

THE TRANSFORMATION OF TELEVISION PROGRAMS IN THE CONVERGENCE OF MEDIA: CASE STUDY ON SHANXI RADIO AND TELEVISION STATION

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ABSTRACT

The escalating growth of new media has profoundly reshaped China's media environment, prompting traditional powerhouses such as Television Stations to adapt and innovate. As China experiences rapid socio-economic growth and a marked enhancement in the rise of China, its television industry faces a unique set of possibilities and hurdles. New media technologies are pivotal in augmenting productivity and redefining organizational frameworks, and the continuous evolution of media convergence significantly drives the transformation within China's TV sector. This paper scrutinizes the metamorphosis of Shanxi Radio and Television Station's television programs, examining various dimensions, including content, technology, and policy. This study proposes a blueprint for integrating effective communication strategies within China's media industry. It also provides an in-depth analysis of the strategic communication techniques employed by Shanxi Radio and Television Station to engage its audience and stakeholders.

Keywords: Television Program; Media Convergence; Transformation

INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND

Television has long been a dominant medium in the field of mass communication, serving as a powerful tool for disseminating information, entertaining audiences, and shaping public opinion. However, with the advent of new media technologies and the rapid development of the internet, the media landscape has undergone a transformative shift. The convergence of media, brought

about by integrating traditional and digital platforms, has disrupted the traditional television industry and prompted a need for adaptation and innovation.

China, as one of the world's largest media markets, has experienced substantial socio-economic growth and witnessed the rise of its television industry. The proliferation of new media platforms and changing audience behaviors have presented opportunities and challenges for television stations in the country. As viewers increasingly consume content across multiple devices and channels, the traditional boundaries between television, the internet, and other forms of media have blurred. To remain competitive and relevant in this evolving media landscape, television stations in China have embarked on a transformation journey, leveraging media convergence to reshape their programming strategies.

One notable case study in transforming television programs in media convergence is the Shanxi Radio and Television Station. Located in the province of Shanxi in China, the station has recognized the need to adapt to the changing media environment. It has implemented various strategies to stay connected with its audience and stakeholders. This case study examines the metamorphosis of television programs at Shanxi Radio and Television Station, focusing on key dimensions such as content, technology, and policy.

The Figure 1 conceptual framework guiding this study is the concept of media convergence, which emphasizes the blending and integration of different media platforms. Media convergence not only refers to the technological aspect of merging various forms of media but also encompasses the organizational and cultural changes required to adapt to this convergence. By analyzing the transformation of television programs at Shanxi Radio and Television Station through the lens of media convergence, this study seeks to identify effective communication strategies that can be integrated into the broader Chinese media industry.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The primary objectives of this research are twofold: First, to explore how media convergence has influenced the content, technology, and policy aspects of television programs at Shanxi Radio and Television Station. Second, to provide an in-depth analysis of the strategic communication techniques employed by the station to engage its audience and stakeholders in the context of

media convergence. By studying the transformation of television programs in this specific case, valuable insights can be gained that may inform and inspire other television stations in China and beyond.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The transformation of television programs in media convergence has been a subject of extensive research and scholarly inquiry in recent years. With the rapid advancement of new media technologies and the changing media landscape, television stations worldwide have been compelled to adapt and innovate to stay relevant in an increasingly digital and interconnected world. This literature review aims to provide an overview of the existing research conducted between 2020 and 2022, focusing on the transformation of television programs within the context of media convergence, specifically emphasizing the case study of Shanxi Radio and Television Station in China.

As a theoretical framework, media convergence has gained significant attention in the study of media industries and their transformation. Scholars have highlighted the blending and integration of various media platforms, including television, the internet, and mobile devices, as key drivers of change in the television landscape. According to Jenkins (2014), media convergence encompasses both technological and cultural shifts, resulting in the convergence of content, distribution, and audience engagement. This convergence has led to the transformation of television programs, affecting their content, production processes, and modes of consumption.

One prominent aspect of the transformation of television programs in media convergence is the reimagining and diversifying content. Scholars have explored the changes in storytelling techniques, narrative structures, and thematic elements in television programming. Li and Liang (2021) argue that media convergence has facilitated the creation of immersive and interactive content, blurring the boundaries between traditional television shows and online platforms. This shift has allowed for more personalized and participatory viewing experiences as viewers increasingly engage with television programs through social media platforms, interactive apps, and user-generated content.

Adopting new technologies has played a crucial role in transforming television production processes. Researchers have examined the impact of digital technologies, such as high-definition cameras, virtual reality, and augmented reality, on the production and presentation of television programs. Langa et al. (2021) suggest that integrating these technologies has enabled television stations to enhance the visual quality of their programs, create immersive viewing experiences, and experiment with innovative storytelling techniques. Additionally, data analytics and artificial intelligence use in content recommendation and audience targeting have become increasingly prevalent in the television industry (Anantrasirichai & Bull, 2022).

Television programs' transformation in media convergence is also shaped by policy and regulatory frameworks. Scholars have examined media convergence's regulatory challenges and opportunities, particularly in China. Taeihagh (2021) discusses how Chinese media regulators have responded to the changing media landscape, highlighting the need for flexible and adaptive policies that foster innovation while ensuring social stability. Policy changes, such as the loosening of restrictions on online video platforms and the promotion of cross-media collaborations, have influenced the strategies and practices of television stations like Shanxi Radio and Television Station.

DISCUSSION

CHANGES IN TV PROGRAM CONTENT AND PRESENTATION

The landscape of television program content and presentation has undergone considerable changes, with non-news and news programs evolving to meet audience demands and adapt to the dynamic media environment. As Shanxi Radio and Television Station continue to innovate and experiment with new formats and storytelling techniques, the future of television programming promises to be diverse, engaging, and reflective of our complex world.

Non-news programs have been socialized and produced as enterprises early on, allowing them to produce content free from policy restrictions as long as it conforms to mainstream values. The rise of new media platforms has contributed to the regular updating of various entertainment programs and increased audience interaction and topic diversity. Furthermore, the researcher notes a trend toward cultural rationality and specialization in non-news programs (Peters et al., 2022). Lin (2022) discussed the changes in television content and production, particularly in non-news programs, and highlighted the influence of new media platforms on these shifts. The researcher's findings demonstrate the early transformation of non-news programs and their adaptation to new media platforms. The increased focus on cultural rationality and specialization noted by the researcher further underscores the evolution of television content in response to changing audience preferences and technological advancements.

On the other hand, the viewpoint of news reports is developing from single to diversified. The considerable changes in news reporting over time emphasize a shift from government and China Communist Party propaganda to an audience-centred approach, with news programs focusing on people's livelihoods and in-depth analysis. Cushion et al. (2017) found that the rise of new media platforms has influenced the ways journalists create news pieces for various audiences and prompted a greater focus on visual appeal in news presentations. Blumler and Cushion (2014) have contributed to understanding the evolution of news content by emphasizing the importance of in-depth interpretation and analysis in news programs. Their discussions highlight the shifting nature of news production and consumption in response to advancements in new media technology. As the media landscape evolves with the availability of vast amounts of information and the rise of social media, news programs have recognized the need to differentiate themselves by offering more profound analysis and context. This shift towards in-depth interpretation and analysis in news programming aims to provide added value to audiences in an era of abundant information and diverse sources. News programs can enhance audience engagement, foster critical thinking, and contribute to a more informed society.

Moreover, news programs are still severely restricted. Despite the shift toward reporting on public life, there is a continued emphasis on promoting government narratives in news dissemination, and traditional media serves as a key platform for the Party and the state's messaging. The Chinese government maintains a strong oversight over news program content to ensure alignment with policies and positions. Repnikova and Fang (2018) found that the Chinese government exercises significant influence over news media to maintain accuracy through responsible oversight.

TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENTS IN TV PRODUCTION

The utilization of digital technology in media production has had a profound impact on both the production process and the audience experience (Sullivan, 2019). Specifically, the application of digital technology, virtual technology, animation, and big data analysis has significantly enhanced the efficiency and quality of program production. This is evident in the ultra-high-definition studio of Shanxi TV Station, where these technologies are harnessed to create compelling TV programs. By leveraging digital technology, Shanxi Radio and Television's ultra-high-definition studio can produce visually stunning content with enhanced clarity and precision (Figure 2). High-definition cameras capture intricate details, while robot-controlled cameras offer dynamic and precise shots, elevating the visual aesthetics of the programs. Additionally, the integration of virtual technology allows for the creation of immersive and interactive elements, adding a new layer of engagement for the audience.

The introduction of new media technologies like 3D animation, virtual imaging, VR, and AR has broadened the possibilities for TV program production, which is consistent with the research conducted by (Kozinets, 2023), who discussed the transformative potential of immersive technologies in media production. The continuous upgrade of TV production equipment, including cameras, recording equipment, and camcorders, has contributed to higher resolution and advanced functions, elevating program quality (Túñez-López et al., 2020). As shown in Figure 3, It is worth noting that Shanxi Radio and Television Station is also embracing the use of virtual anchors. By utilizing smart devices, real individuals can generate and control virtual hosts, blurring the boundaries between real and virtual personalities. This approach allows Shanxi Radio and Television Station to explore innovative ways of engaging with their audience and delivering content in an interactive and immersive manner.

Figure 2. Ultra HD Studio

Figure 3. Virtual Host

The influence of new media technology on traditional media is powerful (Cunningham & Turnbull, 2020). The findings reveal an increasing presence of new media technologies in traditional media; the utilization of animation and virtual animation techniques in the production process enables the realization of creative concepts and visually captivating storytelling. These techniques bring characters and scenarios to life, immersing the audience in captivating narratives and enhancing their overall viewing experience.

Incorporating big data analysis in TV program production also plays a significant role. Shanxi Radio and Television Station can tailor content to meet audience expectations and interests by analyzing audience preferences, feedback, and viewing patterns. This data-driven approach allows for more targeted and personalized content delivery, ensuring viewers' more engaging and satisfying experiences.

The increasing utilization of new media technology in television production has ushered in a new content creation and distribution era. The "Smart Cloud" platform and the establishment of the "Central Kitchen" in Shanxi Radio and Television Station exemplify the profound impact of these advancements (Duan, 2020). They have streamlined production processes, fostered collaboration, and improved the efficiency of content creation and communication. However, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations and challenges associated with integrating new media technology into traditional media production. By striking a balance between innovation and practicality, television producers can leverage the power of new media technology to create captivating and engaging content that resonates with modern audiences.

GOVERNMENT POLICIES AND REGULATIONS

The Chinese government plays a significant role in promoting media convergence and television development. Government policies and financial support have facilitated the construction of media centers nationwide. The state-owned monopoly operation of traditional TV stations serves as a protective measure, preventing private capital from creating competing stations. These findings are consistent with those of other scholars, such as Yin and Liu (2014), who have also observed the strong government support and policy intervention in developing television and media convergence in China. The national plan to promote television has substantially impacted the industry, as evidenced by the significant investments and strategic focus on media centers.

Excessive restrictions in policies and regulations can disrupt market competition and hinder the development of television, suggesting the need for less restrictive policies that are conducive to the development of mainstream media. This sentiment echoes the concerns of other scholars who have noted that the state nature of traditional media and the public nature of the government can create a rigid and conservative operation capacity, potentially stifling creativity among traditional TV professionals (Xu & Yu, 2022).

However, the formulation of policies is challenging, as decision-makers often face uncertainty and must continuously update policies in response to the evolving landscape of media convergence. Previous research has emphasized the importance of policies that align with technological and social trends to promote the development of the TV industry (Wei & Wang, 2022). Nevertheless, the effectiveness of these policies depends on the development stage and vitality of the targets they face.

The case of Shanxi Radio and Television Station exemplifies the impact of government policies and support in promoting the development of television and media convergence in China. The Chinese government's significant role in facilitating media center construction nationwide is evident in the establishment of Shanxi TV Station's ultra-high-definition studio. Financial support and protective measures, such as the state-owned monopoly operation of traditional TV stations, have contributed to the industry's growth.

Furthermore, the positive policies and regulations aimed at promoting media development have played a crucial role in the success of Shanxi TV Station. The emphasis on uniformity across traditional and new media aligns with the research findings, highlighting the importance of policies and regulations in maintaining quality standards in the internet era. The stricter supervision of TV programs, in response to the rapid dissemination of information and real-time capture technology, ensures compliance with regulations and enhances content quality.

Navigating this delicate balance requires policymakers to continuously update policies in response to the evolving media landscape and technological advancements. The effectiveness of policies depends on their alignment with technological and social trends, as well as the stage of development and vitality of the TV industry. Finding the right balance will foster a conducive environment for the development of mainstream media, ensuring continued growth and innovation in the industry.

The case of Shanxi Radio and Television Station reflects the broader landscape of the government's role in promoting television development in China, highlighting the interplay between supportive policies, regulations, and the need for flexibility to adapt to changing circumstances.

CONCLUSION

This paper analyses the transformation of Shanxi Radio and Television Station within the context of media convergence, focusing on aspects such as TV program content, technological advancements, and policy influences. It involves an exploration of TV program content as guided by audience demand, the evolution of TV production technology, and the impact of broadcasting policies. Through a comprehensive review of pertinent literature and direct observation of Shanxi Radio and Television programs, this study highlights both the opportunities and challenges encountered by traditional Chinese TV media in this dynamic media landscape. The opportunities, notably, include the adoption of advanced technologies like the "Smart Cloud" platform, which has facilitated the establishment of the "Central Kitchen" of Shanxi Radio and Television media, fostering a new system of content production and communication. On the other hand, strategies consist of navigating policy changes, satisfying diverse audience demands, and leveraging financial resources effectively for program development. Importantly, such an administrative directive propels the transformation of the TV industry, condenses the lengthy process of reform and integration, and holds promise in accelerating the pace of media integration.

However, this paper has limitations. Firstly, the scope of the research was limited to the case of Shanxi Radio and Television station, which may not be representative of the broader television industry in China or other regions. Secondly, the research focused primarily on the transformations in TV program content, technology, and policy, but other critical factors such as market competition, viewer behavior changes, and socio-cultural influences on TV program content were not profoundly explored.

Future research could address these limitations by expanding the scope of the study to include other radio and television stations in China or comparing the experiences of stations in different regions to identify commonalities and differences. It would also be beneficial to investigate viewer behaviors and preferences in more depth, as these are key drivers of changes in TV program content. Studies could also explore the impact of market competition and socio-cultural factors on TV program content, which should have been more extensively examined in this study.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

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CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

Nil

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